

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH SECONDARY DEFORMATION OF THE DENTITION

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Abstract

Defects in the dentition can very often lead to deformities that are accompanied by a number of morphological and functional disorders, which leads to occlusal changes that significantly complicate the life of patients. Treatment aimed at eliminating the consequences of secondary deformation is impossible without special preparation of the oral cavity for prosthetics, which will significantly increase its effectiveness .

Keywords: special preparation deformity, occlusal violations.

The frequency of occurrence of dentoalveolar deformities still attracts the attention of many researchers [3.4.7]. In the literature, there are data on the prevalence of pathology that differ significantly from each other, which is due not only to the timing of observations, but also to many other physiological and social factors [1.5.8]. Certain interventions for the removal of individual teeth are accompanied by persistent morphological and functional disorders in the dental system, which are characterized by the displacement of individual teeth in different directions, atrophic or hypertrophic processes in the bone tissue of the alveolar processes. Defects and deformations of the dentition can lead to functional overload of the teeth, traumatic occlusion. In such cases, orthopedic treatment becomes more complicated. There is a need for long-term complex treatment. The main task of this treatment is to restore the functional balance of the dentition, to replace defects in the dentition with orthopedic structures [2.6]

Materials and methods.

We examined 124 patients with neglected secondary deformations of the dentition that arose as a result of partial loss of teeth. All patients were divided into groups. Of those who applied, 44 (35.5%) were men and 80 (64.5%) were women.

Group I - 41 patients (33.06%) with deformation of the occlusal surface

Group II - 34 patients (27.41%) with deformation of the dentition due to supraocclusion of the teeth.

Group III - 27 patients (21.77%) with dentition defects that block the movements of the lower jaw and create traumatic occlusion.

IV group - 22 patients with a decrease in inter-occlusal height.

In all these cases, it is not possible to start orthopedic treatment without special preparation of the oral cavity for prosthetics. The complexity of clinical manifestations dictate a plan of therapeutic measures for the

elimination of secondary deformities. Usually it develops

from surgical, therapeutic and orthopedic manipulations and offers at the beginning the elimination of deformity, and then rational prosthetics.

At the same time, surgical preparation provides for the removal of significantly dystopic teeth in combination with corticotomy and rejection of a part of the hypertrophied alveolar process.

Therapeutic preparation usually comes down to depulping of significantly dystopic teeth.

Orthopedic preparation is aimed at grinding the required amount of hard tissues of the tooth and creating deocclusion. This is achieved by using therapeutic fixed and removable structures with support-retaining clasps or temporary mouthguards.

It is necessary to normalize the occlusion and free movement of the lower jaw beforehand, eliminate all traumatic nodes, thereby avoiding traumatic occlusion. To create favorable conditions for the provision of high-quality orthopedic treatment.

Restoration of the occlusal relationship of the dentition, depending on the deformation, is achieved:

1 By shortening the teeth protruding from the dentition (if necessary, the teeth are pre-depulpated)

2 Grinding masticatory tubercles that create traumatic knots and block the movements of the lower jaw.

3 Production of special prostheses for leveling the occlusal surface. Main complaints

4 Production of orthopedic constructions for interalveolar height.

5 Extraction of teeth and excision of the alveolar process.

In the first group of 41 patients, orthopedic treatment consisted of grinding off the required amount of hard tooth tissues, which made it possible to eliminate traumatic knots.

Patients of the second group of 34 people underwent shortening of the teeth that violated the occlusal

surface. If it was necessary to grind off a significant amount of hard tooth tissue and there was a threat of pulp exposure, preliminary depulping was performed.

In the third group, 27 patients underwent selective grinding: grinding of areas of hard tissue of the teeth, on which contact was concentrated during various occlusal movements. The purpose of selective grinding is to create multiple contact throughout the entire dentition with all occlusal movements.

In the fourth group, 22 patients with defects in the dentition and a decrease in the height of the occlusion underwent complex treatment. The main complaints of patients in this group were: violations of the configuration of the face, pain in the temporomandibular joint and masticatory muscles. Some patients complained of hearing loss, a feeling of congestion and tinnitus, dry mouth, seizures, pain, burning sensation in various parts of the tongue. In these cases, orthopedic treatment is aimed at restoring the interocclusal height and normalizing the function of the chewing muscles and the temporomandibular joint.

The treatment was carried out in a complex manner. The provision of assistance is carried out strictly individually, it includes the elimination of spasm of the masticatory muscles, the restoration of the function of the temporomandibular joint. Thus, the treatment of secondary deformation of the dentition requires the mandatory use of the preparation of the oral cavity for prosthetics, which includes: surgical, therapeutic and orthopedic preparation.

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CHOICE OF OPTIMAL ANTYHYPERTENSIVE DRUG: LOSARTAN VERSUS ENALAPRIL

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ВЫБОР ОПТИМАЛЬНОГО АНТИГИПЕРТЕНЗИВНОГО ПРЕПАРАТА ЛОЗАРТАН ПРОТИВ ЭНАЛАПРИЛА

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Abstract

Arterial hypertension remains an actual problem of all humanity. This article compares the two antihypertensive drugs : enalapril and losartan.

Аннотация

Артериальная гипертензия остается актуальной проблемой всего человечества. В данной статье проводится сравнительная оценка двух антигипертензивных препаратов: эналаприла и лозартана.

Keywords: enalapril, losartan ,arterial hypertension

Ключевые слова: эналаприл, лозартан, артериальная гипертензия

Артериальная гипертония является широко распространенной во всём мире эпидемией и одним из наиболее распространенных факторов риска развития инсульта, инфаркта миокарда, сердечной недостаточности и других болезней сердца и системы кровообращения. Именно поэтому, контроль

уровня артериального давления является эффективным способом снижения частоты развития сердечно-сосудистой патологии.

Ренин-ангиотензин-альдостероновая система (РААС) играет ведущую роль в гомеостазе артериального давления. Ключевым звеном в данной системе является ренин, который и запускает весь